

Basic Private School Principals in Amman University District Practicing Degree of Team Building Skills From Teachers' Perspective

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: October 27,2020</p> <p>Accepted: December 01 ,2020</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords Private Basic Schools, Practising Degree, School Principalm Team Work M Team Work Building</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4302234</p>	<p><i>The study aimed to identify basic private school principals in Amman University District practicing degree of team building skills from teachers' perspective . It also aimed to reveal if there are statistically significant differences between study sample perspectives of practicing degree of team work building skills due yo gender , age,education level and years of experience .. The study sample consisted of 243 teachers.The study concluded that sample subjects' responses ranged between medium to high degree of sample's agreement.Analysis Also indicates that the total mean is 3.81 which means that basic private schools principals in University district in Amman degree of practicing team work building skills .Analysis also indicates that there are no differences in principals practicing degree of team work building skills in private basic school in university district in Amman due to (Gender, Age, Education level and Years of experience) The research rescommends that school principals have to set up team building standards and have to encourage team members to try new methods for performing their tasks. Educational Direcitirate has to train school principals and team work members</i></p>

1. Introduction

Problems that traditional administrations face were probably not paying attention to basic element, which is the human element that forms in group (human team), which is the main engine in any administrative process since traditional administrations depended on material elements and directed their attention to production. And how to increase without paying any attention to the human being. Until the emergence of the human relations movement that gave the human the greatest attention in addition to the material aspects and argued that relations between individuals within any department must be activated in a large and positive way, which is what we call "human team".

Team building requires a management that is aware of the importance of human team in advancing management progress. Due to progress of studies and scientific research and its development in this field, it was highlighted on activation of this human element through specialized programs in order to team building in every administrative, educational or political institution, economic, sports, or social.

So without effective team, good management and high competence in team building and activating its role, administration is confused, and progress in its institutions is slow and unstable, and ultimately leads to outputs that are not at the required and desired level compared to exerted effort.

Modern management has increasingly focused on team idea and organizational restructuring facilitate team's work in the organization. Top management advises employees to encourage team work in their sections. Team has become accepted as a basic necessity in working life and an increasing number of organizations have found that change to team-based on work has major effects. In public sector, tasks were filled with greater comprehensiveness and efficiency, and there was an enrichment of work with increased direct contact with customers and team members providing support to each other in dealing with difficult cases. The work of team helps in improving employee's contents and reducing the labor role. The researcher noted that the reason of delay in Jordanian schools and non advancement significantly compared to advanced schools in other countries.

The Problem Statement:

Educational team development and building that serve educational process requires educational leaders who are distinguished by leadership skills that enhance their ability to perform their roles, functions, achieve distinguished competence level and institutions effectiveness they manage. The school team must possess leadership ability to achieve the goals assigned.

Specifically, the study problem can be summed up in answering the following question:

What is the practicing degree of private basic school principal's team building skills from teachers' perspective?

The main question will be answered by answering the following questions

1- What skills should principals of private basic schools have to build team work?

2- Are there differences in private school principals practicing degree of team building due to (gender, academic qualification and years of experience)?

Study objectives

This study aims to:

1-To investigate principals of private basic schools in Jordan practicing degree of team building skills from teachers' perspective

2-To identify the differences in principals of private basic schools skills of team work building due to (, gender, academic qualification and years of experience)

The Study importance

Theoretical importance

The study adds to knowledge by providing a theoretical framework for basic school principal's skills in team building since research in this field is limited according to the researcher's knowledge

Practical importance:

The Ministry of Education may adopt study results and recommendations and apply it in training programs for basic school principals in order to raise the level of their performance in team building because of its positive impact that reflects on administrative and educational process

Literature Review

Team work is defined as "a relatively limited number of individuals, who interact and communicate between each other. They have common goals they seek to achieve through different functions. The cooperation and interaction between team work members takes place in light of basics and standards that control team's behavior." The British Arab Academy for Higher Education defined team work as "a group whose members focus on one goal. The team does not perform its work properly if each of team members focuses on his own goal." (Mackall, 2012, p.14) pointed out that the concept of a team is a group of individuals whose skills and resources are combined and work with each other to achieve a common goal.

Al-Madhoun and Al-Ajrami, (2011) define team work as "a group of limited numbers that Its members cooperate in light of sense of unity, solidarity and social responsibility to achieve a common work or common goal. While West,(2012, p27) defines team work as "a group of individuals within an organization that performs many tasks that contribute to achieving organization , and these individuals participate in all work tasks

and have the authority, and resources to achieve their goals

Ahmad, (2011)) defined the team building process as a mixture of feedback and non-procedural cues that aim to improve group's productive and behavioral work by focusing on methods of work, procedures and personal relationships.

Objectives of Team Building

Team building has several major objectives one of which is enhancing good communications with participants as team members and individuals. There is also increased productivity and creativity.

Another objective of team building is to achieve better operating policies and procedures thereby motivating team members to achieve goals. It is also aimed at ensuring clear work objectives and a climate of cooperation and collaborative problem-solving. Furthermore team building enhances higher levels of trust and support. With team building, diverse co-workers work well together and there are higher levels of job satisfaction and commitment.

Keplicz & Verbrugge,(2010, 3p) indicate that there is a set of basic determinants for team work namely

- 1- Working together to achieve the general goal.
- 2- - Follow up achievement of team members as one unit
- 3- Helping others when needed.
- 4- Coordinate the tasks of team members so that they do not conflict with each other.
- 5- Communicate among team members to learn lessons learned from success and failure.
- 6- Absence of competition between team members towards achieving the general goal.

Hamdan, (2010) indicates that there are three elements that affect team work building and determine team work degree of effectiveness, these elements are :

- Technical element technical element t means the task to be accomplished, and how difficult it is , the information available about , the different implementation methods, and the necessary tools and equipment to fulfill it.

-Human element It consists of two parts:

A- Team Leader: team leader is in charge of team and is able to motivate individuals to carry out a task to achieve specific goals. Team leader is responsible for achieving coordination, integration and interaction among team members

B-Team members: it refers to the behavior of members that greatly affect team work success in general, in terms of their number, experience, degree of affiliation and loyalty, their willingness to collaborate, their ability to team work, the level of morale and their motives.

-Environmental element : Hamdan,(2012) indicates that environmental element consists of two parts, namely: Team work organization, which has a major impact

: A - the social environment: It refers to the social influences on team in terms of habits, trends and behaviors of individuals. It also refers to the range of relationships that determines relationship of members with others, that frame of relationships that is the basis for organizing any team,

B- Organizational environment: It is the organization or institution in which team work performs its task and the policies, philosophy, goals, plans, resources, incentives system, performance evaluation and training contained therein.

Team work building:stages

The process of building a team is gathering number of individuals, and make them work with each other., The process of team work building is carefully planned event for a group of individuals who are gathered having the same goals within the organization(Shabib, 2019) .Therefore, the team building process goes through several stages namely

forming ,, storming .normalization phase (setting the rules) performance (achievement) termination ,bid phase(, Al-Kumi, 2011)

Previous studies

There are many previous studies that have addressed the subject, such as

GA , et al (2019) study aimed to explore the role which public school principals play in implementing teamwork among K-12 teachers. The study sample consisting of 636 U.S. principals who complete an online survey rating the importance of teamwork, identifying the barriers teachers face when working in teams, and listing the initiatives they have taken to promote teamwork among teachers. The study findings suggest that principals consider teamwork to be very important. The study results also showed that time constraints, relationship concerns, and differences in teaching and experience are the leading barriers to teamwork.

Abu Jerboa (2014) study aimed to identify the reality of building work teams and their role in developing administrative creativity from employees point of view of in Ministry of National Economy (southern governorates). The study used descriptive and analytical approach because it fits with study subject .The study sample consisted of (245). The study concluded that there is a role for work teams in developing creativity, as well as a role for technical component of work teams in developing administrative creativity and there is a role of work team's leadership style in developing administrative creativity

Tinuke. (2013) study reviewed current literature on teams in an attempt to outline some of the attractions and challenges of implementing teams so as to give a realistic preview of what can be achieved through teamwork. Tinuke (2013) study outlines eight key points that have been identified by many authors that may facilitate effective development of teams They are are: "clear goals; decision making authority; accountability and responsibility; effective leadership; training and development; provision of resources; organizational support; and rewards for team success.

Al-Hawamdeh and Al-Adaileh (2012) study aimed to identify the impact of work team characteristics on Jordanian ministries effectiveness. The study used the descriptive and analytical approach. The study population consisted of directors and heads of the working departments. A questionnaire was used to collect the required data. The study found that subjects'perceptions of work team's variable characteristics were high

Population and Sampling

The study population consists of all teachers in the private basic schools in University district in Amman amounting 1072. By applying the sample law the sample size was 283 subjects. 250 questionnaires were recollected. & questionnaire were disregarded due to incompleteness, therefore the total sample is 243 subjects

Data collection methods

Two types of data were collected for the purpose of the study: secondary and primary data. Each of these types is discussed as follows:

1. Secondary data

Secondary data are usually collected at the beginning of the study from various sources, such as books, reference, journals, articles, internet, and theses.

2. Primary data

A self administrated questionnaire was developed according to research objectives and hypothesis. The questionnaire consisted of two main parts. The first part includes the demographic data while the second part includes the questionnaire statements that measure the practicing degree of teamwork building.

Instrument Validity

The research instrument proofed by (4) professors from various universities in Jordan. Their comments and modifications were taken in consideration.

Instrument Reliability

A reliability test was made to test the reliability of the measuring instrument used in this research. The reliability was calculated by using Cronbach's Alpha. The variables are considered reliable if they have a value above 0.6. The results indicate that the total Cronbach alpha score was 91.8%.

: Descriptive Analysis

Table (1)

Variables	Options	Frequency	Percentage%
Gender	Male	128	52.7
	Female	115	47.3
Age	Less than 25	24	9.9
	25 to less than 35	91	37.4
	36 to less than 45	104	42.8
	45+	24	9.9
Education level	Less than BSC	30	12.3
	BSC	139	57.2
	MSC	74	30.5
	PHD		
Experience	Less than 5 years	24	9.9
	5 to less than 10 years	98	40.3
	10 to less than 15	97	39.9
	15+	24	9.9

Table (1) indicated that 52.7% of the sample is males and 47.3% are females, The research sample subjects age was as follows 9.9% of the sample are less than 25 years old , 37.4% of the sample their age ranged from 25 to less than 35 years ,42.8% of the sample subjects their age ranged between 35 to less than 45 years old and finally 9.9% of the sample's subjects are 45 years or more

As for education level, 12.3% of the total sample has less than BSC, while 57.2% of the sample have BSC and 30.5% of the sample have MSC. With respect experience, 9.9% have less than 5 years experience, 40.3% of the total sample have an experience between 5 to less than 10 years, 39.9% of the sample have an experience between 10 to less than 15 years , and 9.9% of the sample have an experience of 15 years and more.

Table(2)

Means and standard deviations of sample's responses regarding Practicing Degree of Team work Building Skills

No.	Question	Mean	S.D	Rank	Level
1	The director selects team members to work in one team	3.78	.903	8	High
2	The manager trains team members to be committed in problem solving participation	3.96	.908	2	High
3	The manager helps team members in understanding each other's behavior	3.89	.782	4	High
4	The manager creates building plan for team work	3.76	.825	10	High
5	The manager develops the spirit of cooperation among team work members	3.68	.925	14	High
6	The manager disseminates positive perceptions among team members	3.86	.921	6	High
7	The manager builds trust among team members	3.63	.947	15	Medium
8	The manager concentrates in his selection on the consistency of skills of team members	3.88	.874	5	High
9	The manager builds open relationships with team members	3.77	.921	9	High
10	The principal assists team members to achieve school's goals	3.69	.771	12	High
11	The manager helps team members to identify their goals	3.75	.916	11	High
12	The manager selects team work members	3.94	.865	3	High
13	The manager trains staff members to improve their performance	3.85	.869	7	High

14	The manager is keen that team members get along well with one another	3.98	.888	1	High
15	The manager holds meetings with team members from time to time	3.69	.991	13	High
	General Mean	3.81	.606		High

Table (2) shows that means of sample subjects' responses ranged between (3.63- 3.98). The results indicate medium to high degree of sample's agreement... Table also indicated that statement no. (14) "The manager is keen that team members get along well with one another." ranked the first with a mean amounting (3.98). Statement no. (7) " The manager builds trust among team members "ranked the last with a mean (3.63).

Table also indicates that the total mean is 3.81 which means that basic private schools principals in University district in Amman degree of practicing team work building skills

Second Main Hypotheses:

There are no differences in principals practicing degree of team work building in the private basic school in university district in Amman from teacher's perspective Jordan due to (Gender, Age, Education level, and years of experience).

Table (3)
Tests of Between-Subjects Effects

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	1.975 ^a	4	.494	1.353	.251
Intercept	103.356	1	103.356	283.158	.000
Gender	1.329	1	1.329	3.641	.058
Age	.006	1	.006	.017	.896
Educational level	.689	1	.689	1.888	.171
5.Years of Experience	.000	1	.000	.001	.981
Error	86.872	238	.365		
Total	3611.969	243			
Corrected Total	88.848	242			

Table (30) indicates that there are no differences in principals practicing degree of team work building skills in private basic school in university district in Amman due to (Gender, Age, Education level and Years of experience).

Results and Recommendations

Above mentioned analysis indicated that means of sample subjects' responses ranged between medium to high degree of sample's agreement. Analysis Also indicates that the total mean is 3.81 which means that basic private schools principals in University district in Amman degree of practicing team work building skills .

Analysis also indicates that there are no differences in principals practicing degree of team work building skills in private basic school in university district in Amman due to (Gender, Age, Education level and Years of experience)

The research recommends that school principals have to set up team building standards and have to encourage team members to try new methods for performing their tasks

Educational Directorate has to train school principals and team work members to prepare creative human resources abilities.

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